

THE CONCEPT OF GENDER EQUALITY AND THE MAIN PRINCIPLES OF ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY.

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Annotatsiya: In this article, we will dwell in detail on the need to distinguish between the concepts of gender consideration and gender expression, and the main principles of gender and gender concepts.

Kalit so'zlar: Gender, gender, biological, social, gender stability, identity.

Before starting the study, we found it appropriate to clarify the concept of gender. Gender is a certain set of characteristics associated with masculinity and femininity (qualities belonging to men or women). The concepts of Gender and gender are not the same. Gender is a biological concept, gender yesa is a social concept.

In the classical system of views, the gender system is considered as a binary system: male (father, breadwinner, warrior) or female (mother, mistress). Each of them has its own set of external attributes and internal qualities, hobbies and social functions. However, modern researchers recognize the abundance of genders. Also, from the moment a child is born, his gender is not determined, or an adult does not identify him, but is created by the fact that the child himself becomes older and begins to realize himself. This is also emphasized by the gender researcher clinical psychologist Diana Erenzaft.

Dr. Christie Oleski, director of the gender pediatrics program at the University of Yelya, is never too early to start talking about her gender with children. At the age of two or three, the child begins to realize himself for the first time and to recognize himself as a boy or girl. Therefore, it would be good for parents to tell their children more about gender and help them deal with gender stereotypes. The ways to do this are listed below.

It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of gender accounting and gender self-expression. Because people often confuse them, says Dr. Erenzaft. Gender identity is the inner feeling of a person: as a representative of a certain gender: not men, women or both of them. However, it is also possible that the gender identity does not correspond to how the people around them imagine it. For example, a woman can feel even stronger emotions, perceptions from men in herself. She feels masculine in herself, even if the people around her identify as women. Sexual self-expression is a way in which a person presents himself to the outside world through clothing, training or name.

It seems that gender identity is not always compatible with gender expression. For example, a boy with a girl's sexual identity can usually express himself through "male" behavior, such as playing with machines.

Olezeski argues that children need freedom to express themselves in a healthy way, and if adults around them do not know the difference between gender identity and self-expression, this can lead to conflicts and misunderstandings. In short, parents often confuse two concepts: they think that a boy in a girl's clothes can be transgender (a boy is a girl). But this can be a completely different situation. That is, it should be remembered that this is just a state of interest and connection with the child. Before talking about the structure, content and significance of this problem, it is necessary to dwell on the concept of gender itself. Gender – derived from the English word “gender” - “breed”, the concept of gender is considered as a social structure that is a mentor of physiological reality. Gender is a universal biological difference between men and women and is the unity of the anatomical and physiological essence, that is, from the biological signs that form the basis for determining the belonging of an individual to the biological sex – male or female. Non-serious differences between men and women relate to their biological characteristics. However, in addition to the biological differences between men and women, there are many differences that are based on biological reasons by their nature, that is, there are many differences in social roles, the division of forms of activity, behavior and psychological characteristics of individuals. As noted, the term gender has been adopted to more accurately differentiate the behavior, social and cultural characteristics of men and women with biologically natural differences between men and women. The introduction of the concept of Gender helps to distinguish between two concepts in the most general sense – the concepts of biological and social gender. In our daily lives, many concepts that are not linked to gender are considered “masculine” or “feminine”. To more accurately distinguish between the concepts of “masculine” or “feminine”, the concepts of “feminine” (“feminine”) and “masculinism” (masculine) were adopted. The introduction of new concepts made it possible to eliminate the biological conflict of masculinity and femininity, and to draw attention to the disclosure of the internal mechanisms of the formation of different cultures from a gender point of view. Anthropologists, psychologists and sociologists argue that gender is determined not biologically, but socially and culturally, and culturally and historically is relative. Sofya Babayan about this: “Gender is a social concept. The impeccable image of a woman or a man is given, the chronological and geographical environment is expressed in the variety, national traditions, ethnopsychology, religion, history and national mentality, etc.”-he writes. Its content, interpretation and expression have changed both within itself and intercultural, and serve as an object of historical change.

Is Gender equality possible? Some countries (Denmark, Sweden, Finland) have already answered this question and put forward the following principles by which gender equality can be assessed based on the study of the phenomenon:

- * participation of women in the political and economic life of the country;
- * equal pay for both sexes;

- * giving leave to men for the care of a child born in a family;
- absence of discrimination at work, climbing the career ladder, mastering any profession;
- gender change if you want.

* Social factors – age, category, race and origin-constitute a separate gender content, expression and experience. Modern sociolinguistics consistently and effectively develops this concept as one of the important foundations for the analysis of sociality as well as its forms. The content of the concept of " Gender " is primarily embodied in the social modeling or organization of gender. Social gender is organized with the help of social practice. In society, a normative system of behavior arises that dictates the fulfillment of certain gender roles; in an appropriate way, a line of imagination arises in this society, which has firmly decided on the characteristics that are "masculine" and "feminine". Gender is the sum of the characteristics endowed by social phenomena, not determined by nature. The cultural mask of Gender – gender is our views on gender within the framework of our own socio-cultural perceptions. In Uzbekistan, too, special attention is paid to issues of Gender equality. Adopted by the legislative chamber on August 23, 2019

The law "on guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men " has become a term for the development of this sphere in our country. [2] □

The state guarantees women and men equal rights when exercising personal, political, economic, social and cultural rights. The state guarantees women and men equal participation in the management of society and state affairs, equal participation in the election process, equal rights and opportunities in the fields of Health, Education, Science, Culture, labor and social protection, as well as in other spheres of life of the state and society. Temporary special measures are taken to ensure the implementation of gender policy by the state in order to achieve real equality between women and men, expand their participation in all spheres of public life, eliminate direct and indirect discrimination by gender, and prevent them. Gender equality occurs when individuals are able to use human rights in the same way, regardless of their social status, gender and other social indicators.

To summarize, some experts believe that the concept of Gender equality is recognized as a concept that has entered from the West. However, this view does not justify itself fully. The reason is that in the Islamic world, in particular in the Holy Book of Quran, there are separate suras that reveal this issue in essence, although this concept is not called by the same name. [At-Tariq (the nightcomer): 14] Gender equality has a long history and means an inextricable connection with the religious and secular world and also shows its proof, although centuries have passed. Today, there are religious and legal foundations of the rules of Gender equality, the development and improvement of which should become the sole goal of all members of our society in order to create a solid foundation for future generations.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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